

22nd March 2024, Barcelona

Dear Space Agencies Representatives,

We, the undersigned representatives of scientific, societal, and stakeholder groups devoted to research, awareness, and action on marine litter and debris¹, write to you as a collective body, joining in our shared commitment to safeguarding the invaluable marine and freshwater ecosystems of our planet. We deeply value the diverse contributions that Space Agencies have made to the field of Earth Observations, and with this letter, we hope to engage in a productive dialogue and outline a path towards advancing the field of remote sensing of marine litter.

Marine litter, and in particular plastic pollution, is one of the most pressing and least understood environmental challenges of our time². Its presence in the water bodies of the Earth threatens both aquatic and marine ecosystems, causing an impact on the well-being and economy of local communities that rely on their resources³. In addition, floating litter can also create anomalies in the Earth Observation of other variables, which can hinder to certain degree the satellite-based long-term records, and in particular, may impact to ocean colour observations. Remote sensing capabilities offer unparalleled opportunities for a comprehensive, global, and standardised observation and analysis of this form of pollution, covering an observational gap almost impossible to resolve by other means⁴. By developing remote sensing technologies dedicated to the detection, quantification and mapping of marine litter, the Agencies can significantly help to our understanding about it, and in particular, its dynamics, sources, pathways, and accumulation zones. Such knowledge is indispensable for the elaboration of evidence-based policies, the implementation of effective mitigating strategies, and eventually to support the monitoring that could be required by the future UNEP Plastic Treaty⁵.

In light of these urgent global concerns⁶, we urge the Agencies to incorporate marine litter as one of their priorities within the framework of the Earth Observation. In advocating for your continued support in the area of Earth Observation for Marine Litter (EO4ML), we respectfully submit the following recommendations for your consideration:

Priority in Research and Development: Allocate the needed resources in initiatives pioneering remote sensing technologies tailored specifically for the detection and monitoring of marine litter, directly and through proxies, including plastic and non-plastic litter, and to exploit the potential impacts the long-term Earth Observation data records may have on this matter.

Building collaboration frameworks: Foster robust and long-term collaboration with international research institutions, non-governmental organizations, societal stakeholders, and local communities. Such partnerships are vital for coordinating the collection of standardised in situ data useful to develop the space related technologies.

¹ Marine litter -in short-, referring to both litter and debris, and to both marine and the general aquatic domain.

² Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S. E., Donges, J. F., ... & Rockström, J. (2023). *Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries*. *Science Advances*, 9(37), eadh2458.

³ McIlgorm, A., Raubenheimer, K., McIlgorm, D. E., & Nichols, R. (2022). *The cost of marine litter damage to the global marine economy: Insights from the Asia-Pacific into prevention and the cost of inaction*. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 174, 113167

⁴ Maximenko, N., Corradi, P., Law, K. L., Van Sebille, E., Garaba, S. P., Lampitt, R. S., ... & Wilcox, C. (2019). *Toward the integrated marine debris observing system*. *Frontiers in marine science*, 6, 447.

⁵ UNEA (2019), 'Compilation of United Nations Environment Assembly resolutions on Marine Litter and Microplastics'.

⁶ UNEP *From pollution to solution: a global assessment of marine litter and plastic pollution*.

Facilitating Data Collection and Accessibility: Ensure that new measurements are collected, and that both data and algorithms are universally accessible to the global community. Open access under the FAIR principles is critical for transparency, as well as to encourage the formation of collaborative initiatives on an international scale.

Support to Capacity Building: Dedicate resources to initiatives aimed at empowering local communities and pertinent stakeholders with the required knowledge and expertise to use effectively remote sensing data for marine litter monitoring and management.

Work towards Policy Advocacy: Engage actively with policymakers at regional, national, and international levels to foster the transfer of science knowledge gleaned from these efforts into marine litter policies and regulations. In doing so, the Agencies can facilitate evidence-driven decision-making and encourage the formulation of impactful environmental policies.

We firmly believe that the incorporation of marine litter into the Earth Observation programmes, as an application target, will mark a significant stride towards tackling this environmental issue. The knowledge obtained from advancing remote sensing technologies will not only help environmental preservation and sustainability efforts but will also underpin global initiatives aimed at mitigating marine pollution.

We express our profound gratitude for your attention to this matter and for your past and ongoing dedication to advancing scientific knowledge and technology development for remote sensing of marine litter. Please consider continuing your leadership in this topic by setting EO4ML as one of your priorities in the coming years.

Yours sincerely,

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